

Stock Price Prediction

Using machine learning

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Abstract—It involves predicting the prices of stocks to make better decisions regarding investments using techniques of machine learning. In this project, we have developed a system which can predict stock prices by analyzing past stock market data using artificial intelligence.

Keywords—Stock Price Prediction, Machine Learning, Artificial Intelligence, Financial Forecasting, Stock Market Analysis, Predictive Analytics, Data Visualization.

I. INTRODUCTION

The stock market forms an integral part of the global economy and facilitates companies raising money and investment for growing their wealth. Stock price prediction is one of the most difficult tasks since various factors affect the stock market, including economic conditions, financial condition of the company, political happenings, and sentiments among other dynamic factors. Traditional stock analysis requires expertise and cannot handle the vast amount of data generated by the stock market effectively.

Artificial Intelligence and Machine Learning have brought more intelligence and efficiency in stock market analysis. Machine Learning models can help in analyzing the past stock market data, identifying the underlying patterns, and predicting the future stock prices. Such approaches enhance forecast accuracy and eliminate manual analysis.

The project aims at developing an intelligent AI-based Stock Price Prediction System, which utilizes Machine Learning to analyze stock market data and predict future prices. The system will also facilitate market trends analysis, visualization of data, and generation of dashboards.

II. LITERATURE REVIEW

A. Machine Learning Algorithms for Stock Prediction

Machine Learning algorithms utilized for stock market prediction include Linear Regression, which predicts the stock price from historical data. Other algorithms include Decision Tree and Random Forest that recognize the underlying patterns in stock prices, making them useful for prediction purposes.

B. Predictive Analysis Techniques

Predictive analytics employs past stock market data to make future predictions. Scientists have applied data mining and Machine Learning to increase the prediction accuracy. Such systems allow the stockholders to learn more about how the market works and make appropriate decisions.

C. Existing Challenges

The current stock prediction systems suffer from the problems like poor prediction accuracy, lack of real-time prediction capabilities, inefficient visual representations, inability to scale, as well as the lack of user-friendly interfaces.

D. Research Gap

An intelligent, real-time, and scalable stock prediction system that will employ various Machine Learning models, visual dashboards, and a user-friendly interface does not exist yet. Therefore, this study attempts to fill the existing research gap.

III. EXISTING SYSTEM

A. Conventional Stock Market Analysis Techniques

Conventional stock market analysis techniques depend extensively on manual computations, expert advice, and interpretation of historic data. These techniques are inefficient because they take too much time and are not effective when it comes to analyzing vast amounts of data.

B. Drawbacks of Current Approaches

The current approaches have very limited accuracy of forecasting and do not offer any real-time analysis. They also lack visual representation of graphs and personalized predictions for individual users.

C. Why We Need an Alternative Approach

An alternative approach that will help analyze the market data and produce reliable forecasts with the help of Machine Learning algorithms should be developed.

IV. PROPOSED SYSTEM

A. System Description

The system is a web application developed using machine learning techniques to predict stock prices based on past stock market data. This system helps to analyze stocks and generate graphical results for making well-informed decisions.

B. System Architecture

The components of the system include:

- React for frontend
- Flask for backend
- MySQL database
- TensorFlow and scikit-learn machine learning libraries.

C. Modules in the System

TABLE I. MODULES IN THE S

Module ID	Modules in the System		
	Module Name	Description	
M1	User Authentication	Handles user registration, login, and access control.	U
M2	Stock Data Collection	Collects historical stock market data from sources.	Sto
M3	Data Preprocessing	Cleans, transforms, and prepares data for model.	Ri
M4	Prediction Module	Predicts future stock prices using ML algorithms.	Pi

Fig. 1. Example of a figure caption. (figure caption)

Figure 1 illustrates the different modules involved in the proposed stock price prediction system. The system consists of modules such as User Authentication, Stock Data Collection, Data Preprocessing, Prediction Module, Visualization Module, and Report & Analysis Module. Each module performs a specific function including data collection, processing, prediction, visualization, and report generation. These modules work together to provide accurate stock market analysis and future stock price prediction using Machine Learning techniques.

D. Features of the System

- Predict stock prices
- Trends analysis in the stock market
- Graphical representation
- Comparison of predictions

- Reporting through real-time dashboards

V. IMPLEMENTATION

A. Technology Utilized

- Front-end: HTML, CSS, JavaScript, React
- Back-end: Flask
- Database: MySQL
- Machine Learning Frameworks: Pandas, NumPy, Scikit-learn, TensorFlow, Keras

B. Steps Involved in the Development Process

- Data Gathering
- Data Cleaning
- Training Model
- Making Predictions
- Creating a Dashboard

C. Dataset Used

The dataset involved consists of:

- Open Price
- Close Price
- High Price
- Low Price
- Volume.

VI. CONCLUSION AND DISCUSSION

The system was tested using historical stock market datasets. The Machine Learning models successfully analyzed trends and generated stock price predictions with improved accuracy. The graphical dashboards helped users understand market behavior and compare predicted prices with actual prices.

The prediction accuracy depends on:

- Quality of training data
- Market volatility
- Choice of Machine Learning algorithm

The results show that Machine Learning techniques can improve stock market forecasting and support better investment decisions.

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